

Testing correlation between **size (dbh in cm)** and **Elliptical score from TomatoAnalyzer**:
Pearson's correlation test (whether there is a linear correlation):

Pearson's product-moment correlation

```
data: dbh_csv$dbh_cm and dbh_csv$EllipsoidTA
t = 0.06926, df = 32, p-value = 0.9452
alternative hypothesis: true correlation is not equal to 0
95 percent confidence interval:
 -0.3272780  0.3489636
sample estimates:
      cor
0.01224265
```

However, because dbh_cm is skewed (more trees have lower dbh), Spearman's test of ranked correlation is more appropriate:

Spearman's rank correlation rho

```
data: dbh_csv$dbh_cm and dbh_csv$EllipsoidTA
S = 8516.1, p-value = 0.08348
alternative hypothesis: true rho is not equal to 0
sample estimates:
      rho
-0.3011616
```


Both results show that there is no statistically significant correlation between dbh and elliptical score from TA.

Testing correlation between size (dbh in cm) and Elliptical score from Garryanalyzer:

Pearson's product-moment correlation

```
data: dbh_csv$dbh_cm and dbh_csv$Garryanalyzer_ellip
t = -0.42604, df = 32, p-value = 0.6729
alternative hypothesis: true correlation is not equal to 0
95 percent confidence interval:
 -0.4030314  0.2699194
sample estimates:
      cor
-0.07510139
```

Spearman's rank correlation rho

```
data: dbh_csv$dbh_cm and dbh_csv$Garryanalyzer_ellip
S = 8235.1, p-value = 0.1403
alternative hypothesis: true rho is not equal to 0
sample estimates:
      rho
-0.2582321
```


Both results show that there is no statistically significant correlation between dbh and elliptical score from Garryanalyzer.

Testing correlation between **size (dbh in cm)** and **Petiole/blade length ratio**:

Pearson's product-moment correlation

```
data: dbh_csv$dbh_cm and dbh_csv$PBRatio
t = 0.59558, df = 32, p-value = 0.5556
alternative hypothesis: true correlation is not equal to 0
95 percent confidence interval:
 -0.2420288  0.4277274
sample estimates:
      cor
0.1047067
```

Spearman's rank correlation rho

```
data: dbh_csv$dbh_cm and dbh_csv$PBRatio
S = 8255.1, p-value = 0.1355
alternative hypothesis: true rho is not equal to 0
sample estimates:
      rho
-0.2612881
```


Both results show that there is no statistically significant correlation between dbh and petiole/blade length ratio.

Testing correlation between **blade length (approx. for leaf maturity) and Elliptical score from TomatoAnalyzer:**

Blade length distribution is slightly right skewed (with more leaves having smaller blade length).
Running both Pearson and Spearman.

Pearson's product-moment correlation

```
data: dbh_csv$Blade_Length and dbh_csv$EllipsoidTA
t = 0.34007, df = 40, p-value = 0.7356
alternative hypothesis: true correlation is not equal to 0
95 percent confidence interval:
 -0.2543911  0.3518807
sample estimates:
      cor
0.05369156
```

Spearman's rank correlation rho

```
data: dbh_csv$Blade_Length and dbh_csv$EllipsoidTA
S = 12196, p-value = 0.9411
alternative hypothesis: true rho is not equal to 0
sample estimates:
      rho
0.01175088
```


Both results show that there is no statistically significant correlation between blade length and elliptical score from TA.

Testing correlation between blade length and Elliptical score from Garryanalyzer:

Pearson's product-moment correlation

```
data: dbh_csv$Blade_Length and dbh_csv$Garryanalyzer_ellip
t = 0.99032, df = 40, p-value = 0.328
alternative hypothesis: true correlation is not equal to 0
95 percent confidence interval:
 -0.1565953  0.4380348
sample estimates:
      cor
0.1546989
```

Spearman's rank correlation rho

```
data: dbh_csv$Blade_Length and dbh_csv$Garryanalyzer_ellip
S = 11554, p-value = 0.6874
alternative hypothesis: true rho is not equal to 0
sample estimates:
      rho
0.06377117
```


Both results show that there is no statistically significant correlation between blade length and elliptical score from Garryanalyzer.

Testing correlation between blade length and petiole/blade length ratio:

Pearson's product-moment correlation

```
data: dbh_csv$Blade_Length and dbh_csv$PBRatio
t = 0.68144, df = 40, p-value = 0.4995
alternative hypothesis: true correlation is not equal to 0
95 percent confidence interval:
 -0.2034295  0.3980952
sample estimates:
      cor
0.1071253
```

Spearman's rank correlation rho

```
data: dbh_csv$Blade_Length and dbh_csv$PBRatio
S = 11898, p-value = 0.8211
alternative hypothesis: true rho is not equal to 0
sample estimates:
      rho
0.0358966
```


Both results show that there is no statistically significant correlation between blade length and petiole/blade length ratio.